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REVIEW ON NIGHANTU AADARSH – AN IMPORTANT AYURVEDIC LAXICON

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Abstract

In Ayurvedic classics, herbs occupy an important place, so various Ayurvedic scholars started compiling Nighantu giving details of drugs in terms of synonyms, pharmacological attributes and therapeutic indications. The Nighantu literature is one of the significant facets in the study of Ayurveda and as specially in the subject of *Dravyaguna Vijnana*. In the tradition of Ayurvedic Nighantu, Nighantu Aadarsh is one of the important Nighantu. This work is one of the earliest work on *Dravyaguna* during modern period. It is composed by Shree Bapalal Vaidhya in 19th century. This Nighantu has 127 Varga and 572 drugs. This Nighantu was published in 2 volumes. In this Nighantu, along with ancient medicinal drugs, some new drugs are also described. The objective of this review is to analyse the importance and utility of Aadarsh Nighantu

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Introduction:

The word Nighantu is based on the term *Nigama*. The etymology of the term *Nigama* is that which brings out extremely secret meaning of word. Nighantu may be defined as a glossary containing name of drugs, synonyms, plants, animals, minerals or anything that is administered either food or medicine to the human body. The Nighantu contained synonyms which throw light on different aspects of the entity and thus expose their hidden meaning. The ancient Nighantu were actually like *Kosa* containing synonyms of *Dravya*. But later Nighantu contains properties, actions and uses of *Dravyas*. Nighantu Aadrash is one of the earliest work on *Dravyaguna* during modern period. This work deals with individual *Dravya* and their *Nirukti* & properties.¹

Author of Nighantu Aadrash:

The author of this work is Shree Vaidya Bapalal. He was born on 17th September 1896 at Sanasli in Panchmahal District of Gujarat. He studied Botany from Jayakrishna Indraj, a well-known Botanist of Gujarat. He explored the flora of Barda Mountain, which was written in Gujarati by Jayakrishna Indraj. He came in contact with Yadavji Trikamji Acharya and discussed many plants with him and worked with him in many committees. After studying Nighantu and books on Botany he was inspired to write Nighantu Adarsa.²

His contribution in Ayurveda field:

1. Retired Principal of Shree O.H. Nazar Ayurved College, Surat (1945-1960).
2. Formerly Dean, Ayurvedic Faculty, Gujarat University.
3. Chairman of *Sandigdha Aushadha Nirnayaka Samiti*, Pharmacopeia Committee (Ministry of Health, New Delhi).
4. Chairman of Standard Drugs and Herbs committee, Bombay.
5. Superintendent of Shree Atmananda Saraswati Ayurveda Hospital, Surat.³

Date of Nighantu Aadrash:

This work was published in Gujarati language in 1928 and presented in two volumes. The second edition in Gujarati language published in 1966. Later it was translated into Hindi language in 1968 into two volumes and published by Chaukhambha Bharati Academy, Varanasi.

Text of Nighantu Aadrash:

As already mentioned, the book is presented in two volumes as *Purvardha* Volume I and *Uttarardha* Volume II. He has given about the Basic principles of *Dravyaguna* in the beginning of the 1st Volume. He has also mentioned and discussed about the some of the Nighantu while describing the drugs. In this Nighantu, the author has given *Nirukti* for each *Dravya*. Modern Botanical descriptions have been included because of his knowledge in the field of Botany. Elaborate description of *Dravya* from Samhita period to modern period have been mentioned in this work. He has dealt with 572 drugs in this Nighantu. The morphology of the drug, properties, posology, formulations and some of the Unani drugs have been

mentioned. As he was well versed in Botany and Botanical floras, he has started the classification or grouping of the drugs with Ranunculaceae family but he has not maintained the order.⁴

Preface written in Nighantu Aadrash⁵

- Importance of tree
- Medicinal value of plants
- History of Indian flora
- Short description about Ayurvedic Texts
- Chronological development of Indian medicinal plants
- Basic principle of *Dravyaguna*
- Basic principle of *Dosh-Dhatu-Mala*
- Botanical description
- What is Nighantu?
- Some controversial drugs
- Some definition of *Bhaishajya Kalpana* related words
- Some definition of Nighantu related words

At The End of Each Volume⁶

- Index of Latin and English names
- Index of Sanskrit languages words
- Index of Hindi and other language words
- Index according to disease related drug names

Description of drug

Volume-1: 74 family and 331 drugs

Volume-2: 53 family and 241 drugs

- Common family characteristics
- Vernacular name with Latin name
- *Nirukti* of synonyms of drug
- Habitat of drug
- Chemical constituents of drug
- Useful part of drug
- *Rasapanchak* of drug

- Botanical description of drug
- *Guna* and *Karma* according to various text
- *Aamayik prayoga* of the drug from various text
- Explanatory statement of the drug with its controversy and current era
- Dose of the drug
- Formulations

The classification is as follows:⁷

No.	Name of Varga	Family	No. of drugs	Name of drugs
1	<i>Vatsanabhadi Varga</i>	Ranunculaceae	6	<i>Vatsanabha, Ativisha, Nirvisha, Mamira, Kalounji, Udasaleeb</i>
2	<i>Bhavyadi Varga</i>	Dileniaceae	1	<i>Bhavya</i>
3	<i>Svarnachampakadi Varga</i>	Magnoliaceae	2	<i>Swarna Champaka, Badiyana Khatai</i>
4	<i>Sitaphaladi Varga</i>	Annonaceae	2	<i>Sitaphala, Asopalav</i>
5	<i>Guduchyadi Varga</i>	Menispermaceae	4	<i>Guduchi, Simhaltikta, Patalgarudi, Patha</i>
6	<i>Daruharidradi Varga</i>	Berberidaceae	2	<i>Daruharidra, Vanavrunataka</i>
7	<i>Kamaladi Varga</i>	Nymphaeaceae	2	<i>Kamal, Makhanna</i>
8	<i>Ahiphenadi Varga</i>	Papaveraceae	2	<i>Ahiphena, Satyanashi</i>
9	<i>Parpatadi Varga</i>	Fumariaceae	1	<i>Parpata</i>
10	<i>Rajikadi Varga</i>	Cruciferae	9	<i>Rajika, Mulak, Sarshapa, Khubkala, Dalamalini, Todari, Chandrashura, Grunjanaka, Tarmira</i>
11	<i>Kariradi Varga</i>	Capparidaceae	6	<i>Karira, Varuna, Kabr, Grudhranakhi, Hemakanda, Tilaparni</i>
12	<i>Vanafsadi Varga</i>	Violaceae	1	<i>Vanafsa</i>
13	<i>Katiradi Varga</i>	Cochlospermaceae	6	<i>Katira</i>
14	<i>Tuvarakadi Varga</i>	Flacortiaceae	1	<i>Tuvaraka</i>
15	<i>Lonikadi Varga</i>	Portulacaceae	1	<i>Lonika</i>
16	<i>Jhabukadi Varga</i>	Tamaricaceae	1	<i>Jhabuk</i>
17	<i>Nagapushpadi Varga</i>	Guttiferae	7	<i>Nagakesara, Surapunnaga, Punnaga, Vrukshamla, Mangustaan, Kankustha, Amlavetas</i>
18	<i>Chai Varga</i>	Ternstramiaceae	1	<i>Chai</i>

19	<i>Shaladi Varga</i>	Shaladi	4	<i>Shal, Sarjarasa, Gajarna, Bhimseni Karpura</i>
20	<i>Karpasadi Varga</i>	Malvaceae	11	<i>Karpasi, Bala, Atibala, Japa, Bandhuk, Bhenda, Parisha, Khatmi, Khubaji, Latakasturika, Ambalika</i>
21	<i>Shalmalyadi Varga</i>	Bombacaceae	4	<i>Shalamali, Mocharasa, Goraksha Chinch, Duriyaan</i>
22	<i>Muchukundadi Varga</i>	Sterculiaceae	4	<i>Muchukunda, Pishacha Karpasa, Aavartani, Koko</i>
23	<i>Dhanvanadi Varga</i>	Tiliaceae	5	<i>Dhanvana, Parushaka, Chanchu, Kantaphali, Nagabala</i>
24	<i>Rudraksh Varga</i>	Eleocarpaceae	1	<i>Rudraksha</i>
25	<i>Atsyadi Varga</i>	Linaceae	1	<i>Atasi</i>
26	<i>Kokenadi Varga</i>	Erythroxylaceae	1	<i>Koken</i>
27	<i>Madhvilatadi Varga</i>	Malpighiaceae	1	<i>Madhvilata</i>
28	<i>Laghu Gokshuradi Varga</i>	Zygophyllaceae	2	<i>Laghu Gokshura, Dhanvayasa</i>
29	<i>Changeryadi Varga</i>	Oxalidaceae	2	<i>Changeri, Karmaranga</i>
30	<i>Bijapurakadi Varga</i>	Rutaceae	11	<i>Naranga, Bijapura, Kapittha, Bilva, Harmal, Dahan, Sitab, Tejovati, Tumburu, Nimbuka, Kaidarya</i>
31	<i>Ingudyadi Varga</i>	Simarubaceae	3	<i>Ingudi, Arlu, Bangali Bharangi</i>
32	<i>Guggulyadi Varga</i>	Burseraceae	3	<i>Guggulu, Bola, Shallaki</i>
33	<i>Nimbadi Varga</i>	Meliaceae	3	<i>Nimba, Mahanimba, Mamsa Rohini</i>
34	<i>Jyotishmatyadi Varga</i>	Celastraceae	3	<i>Jyotishmati, Vikantaka, Bhutakesha</i>
35	<i>Badaradi Varga</i>	Rhamnaceae	1	<i>Badara</i>
36	<i>Drakshadi Varga</i>	Vitaceae	3	<i>Draksha, Amlaparni, Asthisrunkhla</i>
37	<i>Feniladi Varga</i>	Sapindaceae	5	<i>Arishtaka, Nayfataki, Lichi, Sanam, Koshamra</i>
38	<i>Bhallatakadi Varga</i>	Anacardiaceae	10	<i>Bhallataka, Amrataka, Tintidika, Rumi Mastagi, Karkatshrungi, Mukulak, Amra, Kajutaka, Priyala, Gudamanjari</i>
39	<i>Shigruadi Varga</i>	Moringaceae	1	<i>Shigru</i>
40	<i>Shimbi Varga</i>	Leguminoceae	-	-
41	<i>Palashadi Varga</i>	Papilionaceae	38	<i>Palasha, Mudgaparni, Mashaparni, Masha, Aparajita, Kulattha, Aadhaki, Shimshapa, Beejaka, Ashwabala, Kalay, Tinisha, Guvak, Karanj, Bhushimbi, Vidarikanda, Vartul Kalay, Soyabeen,</i>

				<i>Masur, Mudga, Makustha, Raajmasha, Nishpav, Shan, Methika, Neeli, Zilla, Bakuchi, Sharpunkha, Agatsya, Itkat, Jayanti, Dusparsha, Yestimadhu, Prishniparni, Shalaparni, Gunja, Kapikacchu, Paribhadra</i>
42	<i>Putikarnjadi Varga</i>	Caesalpiniaceae	15	<i>Pooti Karanja, Anjan, Patanga, Ghrita Karanja, Kasamarda, Chakramarda, Chakshusya, Aaragwadha, Aavartaki, Ashoka, Amlika, Ashmantaka, Kanchanara, Siddheshwar, Markandika</i>
43	<i>Babbuladi Varga</i>	Mimosaceae	8	<i>Babbula, Khadira, Irimesa, Saptala, Shirisha, Shami, Virataru, Lajjalu</i>
44	<i>Padmakadi Varga</i>	Rosaceae	12	<i>Padmaka, Sev, Aaluk, Vatam, Taruni, Tanka, Uruman, Alvaluk, Lottak, Kouso, Gandha Priyangu, Bihidaana</i>
45	<i>Pashanbhedadi Varga</i>	Saxifrageae	1	<i>Pashanbheda</i>
46	<i>Jhakhmehayat Varga</i>	Crassulaceae	1	<i>Jhakhmehayat</i>
47	<i>Turushkadi Varga</i>	Hamamelidaceae	1	<i>Tarushka</i>
48	<i>Haritakyadi Varga</i>	Combretaceae	5	<i>Haritaki, Triphala, Dhava, Arjuna, Bibhitaka</i>
49	<i>Jambvadi Varga</i>	Myrtaceae	8	<i>Jambu, Samudraphala, Lavanga, Eucalyptus, Vilayati Mahendi, Kumbhi, Perukam, Kayaputi</i>
50	<i>Dhatakyadi Varga</i>	Lythraceae	3	<i>Dhataki, Madayantika, Dadmari</i>
51	<i>Dadimadi Varga</i>	Punicaceae	1	<i>Dadima</i>
52	<i>Shrungatakadi Varga</i>	Onagraceae	1	<i>Shrungataka</i>
53	<i>Saptarangi Varga</i>	Samydaceae	1	<i>Saptachakra</i>
54	<i>Papaiyadi Varga</i>	Caricaceae	1	<i>Erandakarkati</i>
55	<i>Kushmandadi Varga</i>	Cucurbitaceae	18	<i>Kushmanda, Patol, Katutumbi, Devadali, Koshataki, Karavellaka, Karkotaka, Karkati, Trapusa, Indravaruni, Bimbi, Madhura Alabu, Pittaphala, Shivlingi, Shadrekha, Katunahi, Shankhini, Dhamargva</i>
56	<i>Nagaphani Varga</i>	Cactaceae	1	<i>Nagaphani</i>
57	<i>Varshabhu Varga</i>	Ficoidaceae	1	<i>Varshabhu</i>
58	<i>Jirakadi Varga</i>	Umbeliferae	14	<i>Shweta Jiraka, Krishna Jiraka, Mandukparni, Yavani, Ajmoda,</i>

				<i>Grunjaka, Mishreya, Satapushpa, Hingu, Goushira, Ushaka, Dhanyaka, Chorak, Baspika</i>
59	<i>Ginseng Varga</i>	Araliaceae	1	<i>Naravel</i>
60	<i>Ankoladi Varga</i>	Alangiaceae	1	<i>Ankol</i>
61	<i>Manjisthadi Varga</i>	Rubiaceae	14	<i>Manjistha, Kadamba, Haridru, Madanphala, Nadihingu, Nemali, Shinkona, Bhramar Challi, Kshetra Parpata, Cofee, Prasarini, Epika, Pinditaka, Pinditaka Bheda</i>
62	<i>Jatamansi Varga</i>	Valerianaceae	2	<i>Jatamansi, Tagar</i>
63	<i>Sahdevyadi Varga</i>	Compositeae	25	<i>Sahadevi, Aranya Jiraka, Kustha, Kusumbha, Akarakarabha, Agnidamani, Parasika Yavani, Utkantaka, Chikkani, Himalochika, Rasna, Bhrungaraja, Gojihwa, Sarahattika, Mundi, Bramhdandi, Suryavarta, Kasani, Tereksekum, Ramtil, Ayapan, Pushkarmoola, Damnak, Gaidar, Kuhu</i>
64	<i>Devanal Varga</i>	Campanulaceae	1	<i>Devanal</i>
65	<i>Wintergreen Varga</i>	Ericaceae	1	<i>Gandhapur</i>
66	<i>Chittrakadi Varga</i>	Plumbagoginaceae	1	<i>Chittrak</i>
67	<i>Vidangadi Varga</i>	Myrsinaceae	1	<i>Vidang</i>
68	<i>Madhukadi Varga</i>	Sapotaceae	4	<i>Madhuk, Bakul, Rajadan, Phulvara</i>
69	<i>Tindukadi Varga</i>	Ebenaceae	1	<i>Tinduka</i>
70	<i>Rodhradi Varga</i>	Symplocaceae	1	<i>Lodhra</i>
71	<i>Lohban Varga</i>	Styraceae	1	<i>Lohban</i>
72	<i>Lohban Varga</i>	Oleaceae	8	<i>Jati, Yuthika, Mallika, Kund, Mokshak, Parijat, Jaitun, Shirakshita</i>
73	<i>Piluadi Varga</i>	Salvadoraceae	1	<i>Pilu</i>
74	<i>Kutajadi Varga</i>	Apocynaceae	7	<i>Kutaja, Karamard, Saptaparna, Karavir, Sarpagandha, Tagar Chandani, Barmasi</i>
75	<i>Arkadi Varga</i>	Asclepiadaceae	10	<i>Arka, Arkapushpi, Sariva, Kaknasa, Vruschikali, Jeevanti, Madhunashini, Murva, Antamoola, Gilodya, Soma</i>
76	<i>Vishtindukadi Varga</i>	Loganiaceae	4	<i>Vishatinduk, Papita, Karushkar Lata, Katak</i>
77	<i>Kiratadi Varga</i>	Gentianaceae	3	<i>Kirat Tikta, Mamejaka, Trayaman</i>
78	<i>Shleshmatakadi Varga</i>	Boraginaceae	4	<i>Shleshmataka, Adhahpushpi, Gojihva,</i>

				<i>Hastisundi,</i>
79	<i>Vruddhadrvadi Varga</i>	Convolvulaceae	13	<i>Vruddhadaru, Sakmuniya, Jelap, Kshira Vidari, Sakar Kandak, Akashvalli, Akhukarni, Trivritta, Krishnabeeja, Maryadvalli, Lakshmana, Sankhapushpi, Rudanti</i>
80	<i>Kantakaryadi Varga</i>	Solanaceae	14	<i>Kantakari, Kakmachi, Ashwagandha, Suchi, Kaknaj, Parsika Yavani, Tamrakut, Dhatura, Katuvira, Ragphala, Tamatar Vriksha, Vrintaka, Agnidamani, Aloo</i>
81	<i>Tiktalonikadi Varga</i>	Scrophulariaceae	4	<i>Bramhi, Kulahal, Katuki, Hrutpatri</i>
82	<i>Pataladi Varga</i>	Bignoniaceae	3	<i>Patala, Shyonaka, Rohitaka</i>
83	<i>Tiladi Varga</i>	Pedaliaceae	2	<i>Tila, Brihat Gokshura</i>
84	<i>Vasadi Varga</i>	Acanthaceae	7	<i>Vasa, Parpat, Sheriyaka, Ikshuraka, Kakjangha, Ucchta, Kalmegha</i>
85	<i>Nirgundiadi Varga</i>	Verbenaceae	9	<i>Nirgundi, Jalpippali, Sag, Renuk Beeja, Gambhari, Agnimanth, Bharangi, Vanjai, Timir</i>
86	<i>Tulasyadi Varga</i>	Lamiaceae	10	<i>Tulasi, barbari, Marubak, Parnayavani, Sprruka, Dronapushpi, Phudina, Jupha, Ustakdus, Nilakanthi</i>
87	<i>Ishabagoladi Varga</i>	Plantaginaceae	1	<i>Ishabagola</i>
88	<i>Punarnavadi Varga</i>	Nyctaginaceae	2	<i>Punarnava, Gulbas</i>
89	<i>Apamargadi Varga</i>	Amaranthaceae	7	<i>Apamarga, Kutinajara, Tanduliyaka, Sitivarak, Gorakhaganja, Kantaki Tanduliyaka, Matsyakshi</i>
90	<i>Vastukadi Varga</i>	Chenopodiaceae	5	<i>Vasuka, Upodika, Palakya, Beet Root, Moras</i>
91	<i>Chukrikadi Varga</i>	Polygonaceae	3	<i>Chukrika, Amlaparni, Rajgara</i>
92	<i>Kitamaryadi Varga</i>	Aristolochiaceae	3	<i>Kitamari, Ishvari, Alpaam</i>
93	<i>Pippalyadi Varga</i>	Piperaceae	5	<i>Pippali, Pippali Moola, Maricha, Kankola, Chavya, Gajapippali, Nagavalli</i>
94	<i>Jatiphaladi Varga</i>	Myristicaceae	1	<i>Jatiphala</i>
95	<i>Karpuradi Varga</i>	Lauraceae	6	<i>Karpura, Maidalakdi, Akashvela, Pisa, Twak, Tamal Patra</i>
96	<i>Agurvadi Varga</i>	Thymelaeaceae	2	<i>Agaru, Majriyun</i>
97	<i>Vruksharuhadi Varga</i>	Loranthaceae	2	<i>Vandak, Kismisha Kavali</i>

98	<i>Chandanadi Varga</i>	Santalaceae	1	<i>Chandan</i>
99	<i>Amalakyadi Varga</i>	Euphorbiaceae	19	<i>Amalaki, Dugdhika, Snuhi, Kharsandithuhar, Bhumiamalaki, Lavali, Kamboji, Putranjivak, Dravanti, Vyaghra Erand, Danti, Nagadanti, Jaypal, Arishta manjari, Kampillaka, Eranda, vruchikali, Swarnakshiri, Damvel</i>
100	<i>Vatadi Varga</i>	Moraceae	9	<i>Vata, Panas, Tuta, Shakotaka, Hops, Udumbar, Palaksha, Nandi Vriksha, Ashwattha</i>
101	<i>Chirbilvadi Varga</i>	Ulmaceae	1	<i>Chirbilva</i>
102	<i>Bhangadi Varga</i>	Cannabinaceae	2	<i>Bhanga, Ganja</i>
103	<i>Akshotakadi Varga</i>	Juglandaceae	1	<i>Akshotaka</i>
104	<i>Kataphaladi Varga</i>	Myricaceae	1	<i>Katphala</i>
105	<i>Bhurjapatradi Varga</i>	Cupuliferae	2	<i>Bhurjapatra, Mayaphala</i>
106	<i>Jalavetasadi Varga</i>	Salicaceae	1	<i>Jalavetasa</i>
107	<i>Shaivaladi Varga</i>	Ceratophyllaceae	1	<i>Shaival</i>
108	<i>Somadi Varga</i>	Gnetaceae	1	<i>Soma</i>
109	<i>Devadarvyadi Varga</i>	Pinaceae	6	<i>Devadaru, Sarala, Hapusha, Nikochaka, Talishpatra, Sthoneyak</i>
110	<i>Munjatakadi Varga</i>	Orchidaceae	2	<i>Amarkanda, Salam Mishri</i>
111	<i>Adrakadi Varga</i>	Zinziberaceae	8	<i>Haridra, Karchur, Amra Gandhi Haridra, Vanya Haridra, Ardraka, Tugakshiri, Ela, Kulinjana</i>
112	<i>Kadalyadi Varga</i>	Musaceae	1	<i>Kadali</i>
113	<i>Kesaradi Varga</i>	Iridaceae	2	<i>Kesara, Haimavati Vacha</i>
114	<i>Musalikandadi Varga</i>	Amaryllidaceae	2	<i>Mushali, Naga Damani</i>
115	<i>Anannasadi Varga</i>	Bromeliaceae	1	<i>Parvati</i>
116	<i>Varahikandadi Varga</i>	Dioscoriaceae	1	<i>Varahikanda</i>
117	<i>Lashunadi Varga</i>	Liliaceae	9	<i>Rasona, Palandu, Kumari, Shatavari, Safed Musali, Suranjan, Chopachini, Vanpalandu, Kalihari</i>
118	<i>Vatsapriyadi Varga</i>	Commelinaceae	1	<i>Vatsapriya</i>
119	<i>Taladi Varga</i>	Arecaceae	8	<i>Taal, Kharjura, Pug, Dariyay Narikel, Narikel, Nal, Rakta Niryas, Pam Oil</i>
120	<i>Ketakyadi Varga</i>	Pandanaceae	1	<i>Ketaki</i>
121	<i>Erakadi Varga</i>	Typhaceae	1	<i>Erka</i>
122	<i>Vachadi Varga</i>	Araceae	6	<i>Vacha, Jalakumbhika, Surana,</i>

				<i>Manakanda, Patode, Gajapippali</i>
123	<i>Mustadi Varga</i>	Cyperaceae	2	<i>Musta, Kasheruk</i>
124	<i>Trunadi Varga</i>	Poaceae	18	<i>Durva, Vamsha, Ikshu, Kusha, Hribera, Rohisha Ghas, Ushira, Janbirtruna, Bhutrana, Kutta Ghas, Yava, Dhanya Piyangu, Godhuma, Shali, Kodrava, Gavedhuka, Nivaar, Yaavnaal, Chinak, Shyamaka, Oat, Makai, Barjari, Nagali</i>
125	<i>Hansarajadi Varga</i>	Filiaces	3	<i>Hansaraj, Mayursikha, Sunishnak</i>
126	<i>Bhuchhatradi Varga</i>	Fungii	1	<i>Bhuchatraka</i>
127	<i>Shilapushpadi Varga</i>	Lichens	1	<i>Shaileya</i>

Characteristics of Nighantu Adarsh

- Name of drugs are authentic, confirmative and applicable.
- Drugs of Unani, some other drugs which are not described in Samhita and Texts are also explained.
- Given an idea about market status of drugs.
- Author has tried to give solution of controversial drug by identification characteristics and practical applicability.
- Description of drug used in different geographical area.
- Given maximum vernacular name for identification of drug.
- Given *Amayika Prayoga* of each drug and also share about author's clinical experience.

Conclusion:

Aadarsh Nighantu contains 127 Vargas and name of each Varga starts with the name of first drug. It clears many controversies on medicinal plants and illustrated several exotic plant species, making it a valued treaties for scholars of Ayurveda and Botany. Many new Varga's were described in this Nighantu like, *Erakadi Varga, Bhuchhatradi Varga, Anannasadi Varga, Lohban Varga, Jhakhmehayat Varga* etc. Because of the above-mentioned characteristics, Nighantu Aadarsh occupies an important place among various Ayurvedic Nighantu. This Nighantu presents various new discoveries and substances with their properties till its composition era.

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